

REINFORCING RULE OF LAW AND HUMAN RIGHTS: RATIONALIZING THE BAIL SYSTEM

Dr. Girjesh Shukla *

“The best guarantee of presence [of the accused] in court is the reach of the law, not the money tag.”

—**Krishna Iyer, J. in *Moti Ram Vs. State of M.P.***¹

ABSTRACT

Law providing bail reflects a fine balance between the right to liberty of the person accused of an offence and the interests of state vis-à-vis society. Adversarial Criminal Justice System provides the fundamental rule that unless a person is a proven guilty; s/he shall be deemed to be innocent and would be entitled for all her right to liberties. This rule reverberates in the Indian Criminal Justice System throughout. The off shoots of this principle emulates in various forms such as right to remain silent, proof of guilt beyond reasonable doubt etc. Generally, a criminal trial takes longer time as it requires detailed proof of incriminating facts, opportunity of hearing, examination of witnesses, testimonies, arguments etc., and during all this, the accused is required to be present throughout though being innocent by a legal fiction. Thus, it inevitably mandates his release from detention. Subject to satisfaction of other conditions, judicial system demands furnishing of a bail bond and surety for being released on bail.

* Associate Professor of Law at Himachal Pradesh National Law University, Shimla.

1. *Moti Ram Vs. State of M.P.*[1978] 4 SCC 47.

It has been found, time and again, that system of bail, in practice, violates principle of equality and equal protection of laws being decided arbitrarily. By imposing heavy amount of bond, provisions for technical verifications, poor and indigent were denied their being released on bail even after having appropriate bail order. Though, the law and judicial guideline has set the tone differently, but trial courts have not appreciated this properly, resulting into gross violation of Human Rights, and the rights enshrined in Article 14 of the Constitution of India. The present work empirically tests this hypothesis and concluded that bail jurisprudence need a serious reconsideration.

Key Words: Bail, Bail Jurisprudence, Justice, Bail Bond, Criminal Procedure, Equality.

INTRODUCTION

THE adversarial criminal justice system provides the fundamental rule that unless a person is a proven guilty; s/he shall be deemed to be innocent and would be entitled for all her right to liberties like any other person. This rule reverberates throughout the Indian Criminal Justice System. The off shoots of this principle emulates in various forms such as right to remain silent, proof of guilt beyond reasonable doubt etc. Whenever criminal process is initiated against the suspect of crime, the investigating agencies investigate the offence. Though, there is no compulsive rule which requires the arrest of the accused whenever he has allegedly committed any crime. However, there are three primary justifications due to which wide discretion is being given to the investigating agencies to arrest the suspect. *Firstly*, the accused being the first and foremost source of information about the alleged crime, his presence and questioning him is required during the investigation.² This can best be ensured by his arrest. *Secondly*, in many cases, offenders showing of *flight risk* and/or *non-cooperation* and/or *tampering* with evidence,

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2. The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 s. 161(1). The words 'any person' used in Section 161(1) also include a person who may be accused of the crime and suspects. See, *Pakala Narayana Swami Vs. Emperor*, AIR 1939 PC 47. However, in *Nandini Satpathy Vs. P.L Dani*, 1978 SCC (Cri) 236, the Supreme Court held that the accused person keep his mouth shut if the answers sought has a reasonable prospect of exposing him to guilt in some other accusation, actual or imminent, even though the investigation under way is not with reference to that.

documentary or physical, in such cases the investigating agencies are compelled to arrest the accused. *Thirdly*, the arrest is also made in all those cases where commission of crime is of such nature where there are grave danger of law and order arise due to escalation of violence.

Whatever may be the reason, commission of an offence calls for an in depth investigation, and trial entailing detailed proof of incriminating facts, opportunity of hearing accused, victim and the prosecution; examination of witnesses; testimonies, arguments etc., and thus, the accused so arrested, remains in custody as undertrial prisoners for a very long period. The challenges, including overcrowding of prisons; livable condition therein and the entitlements of undertrial prisoner demands new conceptual inquiry in the bail jurisprudence.

OVERCROWDING OF PRISON: NCRB REPORT

According to the data released by National Crime Record Bureau (NCRB) in 2017, there were at least 3, 08,718 inmates in various jail as undertrials and they constitute 68.5% of total inmates. The number of undertrial prisoners has increased a whopping 9.4% during 2015-17. Uttar Pradesh has reported the maximum number of undertrial prisoners (22.3%, 68,762). A large number of prisoners (90.8%) were languishing in the prisons of their domicile, however no less than 26,048 inmates were imprisoned to prisons of other states.³ Among undertrial prisoners, around 75% of prisoners were confined for a period of less than one year, whereas 34,311 undertrial prisoners were confined for more than 2 years. There were 4,876 undertrial prisoners were confined for more than 5 years. Thus, the data collected by National Crime Record Bureau speaks in volume about problem of undertrials, and thereby narrates the complexities of bail system.

CODE OF CRIMINAL PROCEDURE AND BAIL JURISPRUDENCE

Chapter 33 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (hereinafter referred as Criminal Procedure) provides the law relating bail. This Chapter prescribes law and regulation for bail in bailable offence,⁴ non-bailable

3. Maharashtra has reported the highest number of undertrial prisoners of other states (21.6%, 5,616 inmates) followed by Delhi (12.0%, 3,123 inmates) and Uttar Pradesh (9.0%, 2,340 inmates).

4. CrPC 1973, Section 436.

offence,⁵ anticipatory bail,⁶ default bail,⁷ cancellation of bail,⁸ furnishing bail bond⁹ etc. In bailable offences, 'bail' is the Rule and 'jail is the Exception', and only when the accused refuses to offer bail, he may be arrested. 'Non-bailable does not mean bailable', rather, it is bailable upon satisfaction of certain requirements of law. Criminal Procedure enables the Court of Sessions and the High Courts with anticipatory bail, wherein these courts may issue 'direction' to grant bail to the person in the event of his arrest by the police or acceptance of his surrender.

BAIL BOND AND SURETY: THE PROCEDURE

In addition to the above, there are two other procedural requirements for granting bail i.e. furnishing of bail bond and surety,¹⁰ Bail-bond is a monetary deposit/guarantee whereby accused undertake to observe the terms and conditions laid down in the bail order, and in case of breach of terms and conditions, his bail will be cancelled, and the amount deposited as 'bond', will be forfeited.¹¹ As a general rule, the Courts insist for the production of property documents and the verification thereof, before a formal release of accused may be ordered. In case of land documents enclosed bond, the same is to be verified by appropriate authority, mostly often the Sub-Divisional Magistrate.¹² It further permits of a deposit of a sum of money or Government Promissory Notes, except in the case of a bond for good behaviour, *in lieu* of executing a bond.¹³ Sometimes, *in lieu* of property documents, accused or surety use to enclose the Registration Certificate (RC) of two-wheelers, four-wheelers, etc., and even in such cases verification is done through the Regional Transport Office (RTO). The 'surety bond', is an assurance between the surety and the court, and the same is required to be furnished before the court wherein

5. CrPC 1973, Section 437.

6. CrPC 1973, Section 438.

7. Default bail covers those situations wherein on completion of certain conditions such as period of detention, the arrested person becomes entitle to be released. CrPC 1973 Sections 436A, 167, 389.

8. CrPC 1973, Section 439.

9. CrPC 1973, Section 441.

10. CrPC 1973, Section 441.

11. CrPC 1973, Section 446.

12. Circular Letter No. 58/98 dated 5.11.1998, High Court of Allahabad; Circular No. 28/2010/Admin.'G-II' Dated 18.9.2010 High Court of Allahabad; See also *Shiv ShyamPandey Vs. State of UP*, 2009 (5) ALJ 70.

13. CrPC, 1973, Section 445.

the surety undertakes the appearance of the accused as and when required. If the accused fails to appear, the surety amount could be forfeited after a due enquiry.¹⁴ If any fraud is practiced upon the Court in furnishing surety bond, the Court has the power to cancel the surety bond.¹⁵

Criminal Procedure cautions the courts about the amount of bail bond or surety and provides that every bond should be fixed *with due regard to the circumstances of the case and should not be excessive*.¹⁶ Bail/surety amount is dependent on several factors. There is no provision in law to insist that surety must hail from within the district where the Court is situated.¹⁷ Courts have guided that when the accused is not likely to abscond and has his roots in the community, he can be safely released on personal bond. Enquiry into solvency of the accused can become a source of harassment and often results in deprivation of his liberty.¹⁸ Where sureties are insisted on, ordinarily due weight should be given to the affidavits produced by the surety and an inquiry or insistence on a solvency certificate must be the exception rather than the rule.¹⁹ In few cases, the Apex Court laid down the guiding principles ruling that "when accused if the court is satisfied that the accused has his roots in the community and is not likely to abscond it can safely release the accused on his personal bond."²⁰ To determine whether the accused has his roots in the community which would deter him from fleeing, the Court should take into account the following factors viz length of his residence in the community; his employment status, history and his financial condition; his family ties and relationships; his reputation, character and monetary condition; his prior criminal record including any record of prior release on recognizance or on bail; the identity of responsible members of the community who would vouch for his reliability; the nature of the offence charged and the apparent probability of conviction and the likely sentence in so far as these factors are relevant to the risk of non-appearance; and any other factors, indicating the ties of the accused to the community bearing on the risk and willful failure to appear. The Court further said that "if the Court is satisfied on a consideration of the relevant factors that the accused has his ties in

14. CrPC 1973, Section 446.

15. CrPC 1973, Section 446A.

16. CrPC 1973, Sections 440 & 441.

17. *Moti Ram Vs. State of Madhya Pradesh*, AIR 1978 SC 1594.

18. *Hussainara Khatoon Vs. Home Secretary, State of Bihar*, AIR 1979 SC 1360.

19. *Valson Vs. State of Kerala* (1984) 2 Crimes 503.

20. *Hussainara Khatoon Vs. Home Secretary State of Bihar*, AIR 1979 SC 1360.

the community and there is no substantial risk of a non-appearance, the accused may as far as possible be released on his personal bond.”

An analysis of these provisions would inevitably suggest that whenever a person is arrested, the rule is in favour of granting him bail, and not the jail, unless circumstances suggest his fleeing from justice or thwarting the course of justice or creating other troubles in the shape of repeating offences or intimidating witnesses.²¹ It will further outline that while considering the question of bail, the gravity of the offence involved need to be considered carefully.²² For the purpose of releasing any person on bail, the judicial mind scrutinizes the fact as to whether the release of the accused will affect the fair trial or not.

RE-EXAMINING THE MONETARY TAG OF BAIL ORDER

The concept of bail bond and/or surety seems to be very reasonable procedure to compel the presence of the accused before the court. It is believed that the accused having furnished certain amount of bail-bond can't dare jump the bail.

However, the procedure for furnishing bail bond and surety, so designed, is flawed and violates its own normative requirements. *Firstly*, there are occasions where accused is arrested in some other jurisdictions, far away from his local area, and in such cases accused being a stranger to the area, may not secure a person to stand as surety. *Secondly*, notwithstanding the fact that 'monetary tag' is an accepted norm for granting bail, and the law directs amount so fixed shall not be excessive, it is often seen that the amounts are being fixed arbitrarily high, and thereby deny the accuse quick release. *Thirdly*, as against Section 440 of the Criminal Procedure which demands the court 'to give due regard to the circumstances of the case' and accordingly fixed the bond, various bail orders examined hereinafter suggest that the bail bonds are being fixed arbitrarily without giving due regard to nature of crime, flight risk in the of offender or any other normative criteria. Thus, in practice, it is fixed arbitrarily devoid of any normative criteria.²³

21. *Kalyan Chandra Sarkar Vs. Rajesh Ranjan @ Pappu Yadav* [2004 (7) SCC 528]; *State of U.P. Vs. Amarmani Tripathi* [2005 (8) SCC 21]; *Sanjay Chandra Vs. C.B.I.* [2012 (1) SCC 40]; *Arnesh Kumar Vs. State of Bihar*, [2014 (8) SCC 273].

22. *State of Rajasthan Vs. Balchand*, AIR 1977, SC 2447.

23. *State of Rajasthan Vs. Balchand*, AIR 1977, SC 2447.

The Human Rights Commission constituted under UN Economic and Social Council, through its Report on "Civil and Political Rights, including the Question of Torture and Detention" published on December 12, 2005 questioned the very idea of putting monetary tag on bail, being oppressive against poor:²⁴

"Moreover, in legal systems where pretrial detention is ultimately linked to bail, poverty and social marginalization appear to disproportionately affect the prospects of persons chosen to be released pending trial. Bail courts base their decision whether to release an accused person also on his or her "roots in the community". People having stable residence, stable employment and financial situation, or being able to make a cash deposit or post a bond as guarantee for appearance at trial are considered as well-rooted. These criteria of course are often difficult to meet for the homeless, drug users, substances abusers, alcoholics, the chronically unemployed and persons suffering from mental disability, who thus find themselves in detention before and pending trial when less socially disadvantaged persons can prepare their defence at liberty. As empirical research in many countries has shown that defendants who are not detained pending trial have significantly better chances to obtain an acquittal than those detained pending trial, the bail system deepens further the disadvantages that the poor and marginalized face in the enjoyment of the right to a fair trial on an equal footing."

Imposing arbitrary bond amount was ridiculed by the Apex Court of India since seventies, as being violative of Article 14 and 21 of the Constitution of India.²⁵ The court observed that that the 'money' may be one consideration for creating deterrence, but *per se* cannot be a guarantee for observance of terms and conditions laid down in the bail order.

CRIMINAL PROCEDURE AMENDMENT, 2005

The Parliament of India acted, though very late and in a limited manner, amended the bail law in the year 2005. The present law provides that no indigent person may be asked to pay bail amount, and he will be released on bail, if otherwise his bail is justified.²⁶ It further provides that, if

24. Commission on Human Rights, Report of the Working Group on Arbitrary Detention, December 12, 2005 (E/CN.4/2006/7).

25. *Moti Ram* [n.1].

26. CrPC 1973, Section 436.

any person fails to deposit bail amount in two weeks, he will be deemed to be indigent.²⁷ It is probably agreed that monetary-tag deterrence is a traditional practice, and the changes carried through amendment in the Code of Criminal Procedure in the year 2005, and judicial guidelines reflect modern bail jurisprudence. This new bail jurisprudence suggests that law must not create a whimsical and arbitrary difference between *have* and *have-nots*. Be it rich or poor, if their case comes within the purview of grant of bail order, then their 'being poor' cannot be the ground to deny their fundamental liberty. It is part of fair trial system that accused should not be subjected to a procedure wherein his 'being poor' deny him access to any privilege which is otherwise available to similarly situated individuals.

APPROACH OF BAIL COURTS: MONETARY TAG AND BEYOND

Generally, bail bond is fixed while considering relevant financial status of the accused. In *Motiram* case²⁸ the Apex Court suggested that harsh condition in bail orders are against the law. In *Sandeep Jain Vs. National Capital Territory of Delhi*,²⁹ Supreme Court ruled that bail conditions being onerous in the nature are against law. Further, *Ramathal & Others Vs. Inspector of Police*,³⁰ the Supreme Court did not approve a bail condition ₹ 32,00,000/- and also on their executing a personal bond of ₹ 1,00,000/- with two sureties each for the like sum. Again, the Supreme Court in *Amarjit Singh Vs. State of NCT of Delhi*,³¹ deplored the bail order requiring the applicant to submit the sum of ₹ 15 lacks in the form of FDR, and held the same as 'unreasonable' condition.

Thus, the Apex Court guided that the objective of a bail bond should be to create a financial deterrence, and thereby securing compliance of terms and conditions of bail order, and not the means to deny a proper release of the undertrial prisoner.

However, the approach reflected through various bail order by bail courts seems to be very disturbing. Even, petty cases, like buffalo theft, mobile theft, cycle theft etc., the amount of bail bond is as higher as cases involving attempt to murder or forgery. Whereas, cases where accused

27. CrPC 1973, Explanation to Section 436.

28. *Motiram* case [n. 1].

29. (2000) 2 SCC 66; See, *Sakthivel Vs. Inspector of Police*, [2015 (2) MWN (Cr.) 438].

30. [2009 (3) SCALE 550].

31. JT 2002 (1) SC 291.

being well-off, hardly worried about the monetary tag of the bail bond, the courts have been very liberal in deciding the monetary tag for bail bond. In *Satish Ravilal Shah Vs. State of Rajasthan*,³² where five bail petitions involving super-rich celebrities of Indian cinema were being disposed of under various provisions of Indian Penal Code, 1860, the Arms Act, 1959, and the Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972. In this case, amongst others, film actor Salman Khan was charged for hunting the blackbuck (*Antelope cervicapra*), a preserved animal under the Wildlife Protection Act, 1972. Bail was allowed to each of the accused by furnishing a personal bond in the sum of ₹ 20,000/-. Similarly, prominent politicians were set on bail in the National Herald case, by furnishing personal bond of ₹ 50, 000/- and one surety each.³³ Interestingly, in one case, where a prominent political leader refused to seek bail and furnish any personal bond or surety bond, the court of Chief Metropolitan Magistrate released him on mere and undertaking that he would appear on every date of hearing.³⁴ In another defamation case filed by the then Finance Minister against Delhi Chief Minister, bail was granted by the court of Chief Metropolitan Magistrate by furnishing a personal bond of ₹ 20,000.³⁵

Hereinafter, it is argued that without having a reasonable and substantial difference between the amounts for bail bond between rich and poor; between different classes of accused based on severity of offence committed, creates a serious doubts as to arbitrariness of these bail orders, and thus, violative of Article 14 of the Constitution of India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY, DATA, AND INFERENCES

The work is an attempt to explore as to whether the dictum of Supreme Court in *Moti Ram Vs. State of MP*,³⁶ and the legislative intent

32. *Satish Ravilal Shah Vs. State of Rajasthan*, 1999 Cri LJ 727 (Raj.)

33. 'As it happened: Sonia, Rahul granted bail' (The Hindu, 19 December 2015) <<http://www.thehindu.com/news/national/national-herald-case-security-beefed-up-for-sonia-rahul-at-patiala-house-court/article8007754.ece>> accessed 10 January 2019.

34. 'Kejriwal refuses to seek bail in defamation' (Business Standard) <http://www.business-standard.com/article/politics/kejriwal-refuses-to-seek-bail-in-defamation-case-113060501039_1.html> accessed 10/01/2019.

35. Kaunain Sheriff M, 'Defamation case by Jaitley: Kejriwal, 5 party leaders get bail, as BJP and AAP supporters clash' (Indian Express, 8 April 2016) <<http://indianexpress.com/article/india/india-news-india/arun-jaitley-ddca-defamation-case-delhi-court-grants-bail-to-arvind-kejriwal-5-other-aap-leaders/>> accessed 10 January 2019.

36. *Ibid.*

reflected through Amendments of 2005 are guiding the bail court in its letter & spirit.³⁷

Table 1: Data Profile

District	Number of Bail orders	Judicial Officer		Bail applicant	
		Male	Female	Male	Female
Ghaziabad	50	25	25	48	02
Saharanpur	50	25	25	49	01
Total	100	50	50	97	03

The research methodology used in this work is empirical with a descriptive research design. The sample design is stratified random, and the data were collected from Districts Ghaziabad and Saharanpur of Uttar Pradesh. These two districts represent two different socio-economic and demographic patterns. On one hand Ghaziabad is part of National Capital Territory Region, having high literacy, economic development and legal awareness, the Saharanpur is considered far behind on all these parameters.

For analyzing gender perspective, the judicial officers were selected with stratified random selection process to provide equal representation. Though the bail orders were selected randomly, three bail applicants were female.

Table 2: Category of Offences

Category of Offences	Ghaziabad		Saharanpur		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	
Attempt to Murder/CH	01	Nil	03	06	10
Hurt Simple/Grievous	Nil	01	01	01	03
Theft/Robbery etc.	13	17	10	06	46
Forgery	01	Nil	01	01	03
Arms Act	Nil	Nil	Nil	02	02
Cow Slaughter	Nil	Nil	05	Nil	05
Possession of Drug/Liquor	01	02	05	04	12
Gangster Act	14	Nil	05	Nil	19
Total	30	20	30	20	100

37. Amendment in Code of Criminal Procedure, 2005.

Since the object of this study is to ascertain and describe the fixing of bail bond, required amount for bail bond, and judicial attitude in fixing such amount, the descriptive research design is considered appropriate.

Table 3: Average Monetary Tag in the Bail Bond

Category of Offences	Ghaziabad		Saharanpur	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Attempt to Murder/CH	1,00,000	NA	50000	50,000
Hurt Simple/Grievous	NA	50000	50000	50,000
Theft/Robbery	50,000	50,000	41,111	47,500
Forgery	50,000	NA	50,000	50,000
Arms Act	NA	NA	NA	50,000
Cow Slaughter	NA	NA	60,000	NA
Possession of Drug/Liquor	50,000	50,000	54,000	50,000
Gangster Act	50,000	NA	50,000	NA

Primary data is collected for this study, is analyzed with the secondary data to describe the phenomena. A total of one hundred bail order, fifty each from district Ghaziabad and Saharanpur respectively were selected from the official website of these courts.³⁸ Only those cases were selected in which bail was allowed with or without sureties.

Monetary Tag in the Bail Bond: The data reflects very indiscriminate fixation of amount in the bail bond. There seems to be no criteria and little application of mind as to facts and circumstances while fixing the amount of bail bond.

For example, in case of heinous offences like attempt to murder, culpable homicide the average amount mentioned in the bail bond is ₹ 50,000/. Ironically, cases of theft also met with the similar bail bond. During study, it was found that bail amount for stealing of buffalo or a mobile is not anywhere different to that of attempt to murder.³⁹

The sample size of the work is comparatively smaller, and thus any possible generalization may be subject to further inquiry. However, there are two irresistible findings of this study, *firstly*, that bail courts have failed

38. https://ecourts.gov.in/ecourts_home/

39. Akbar Vs. State, Crime No. 140/2018, District Court & Session Court-09, Saharanpur, 11/05/2018.

to appreciate the rationale behind having differential amount of bail bond, and *secondly*, the bail courts are reluctant in providing reasons behind fixing any given amount against the bail bond. the resultant is an arbitrariness in bail order.

CONCLUSION

Highlighting the need for caution while exercising the judicial discretion in bail matters, KRISHNA IYER, J., observed that: "Personal liberty, deprived when bail is refused, is too precious a value of our constitutional system recognized under Article 21 of the Constitution that the crucial power to negate it is a great trust exercisable not casually but judicially, with lively concern for the cost to the individual and the community.... After all, personal liberty of an accused or convict is fundamental, suffering lawful eclipse only in terms of 'procedure established by law'. The last four words of Article 21 are the life of that human right."⁴⁰ Data released by NCRB, Government of India, suggests that the number of undertrial prisoners are increasing by each new data collection. There is no survey available which may reflect to how many of these undertrials are denied bail due to non-furnishing of their surety. However, the way indiscriminate bail bond is imposed over these accused, study indicates possible denial of bail to many poor fellow citizen. This is not only a violation of fair trial system but also violation of Article 14 and 21 of Constitution of India. One must remember that the best guarantee of presence in court is the reach of the law, not the money tag, and it is high time for the courts to evolve clear and categorical policy for imposing amount of bail bond.

40. *Gudikanti Narasimhulu Vs. Public Prosecutor*, High Court of A.P., AIR 1978 SC 429 at p. 430.